

Impact of Trading Strategies on the Financial Performance of Exporting Businesses. A Case of Small to Medium Enterprises in Cross-Border Trading in Midlands Province, Zimbabwe

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Abstract

The study focused on the impact of trading strategies on the profitability of Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border trading. The main theories guiding the research study are the classical theories of international trade and the “New Trade Theories”. Also, the conceptual framework showed the relationship between the independent variable “trading strategies” and the dependent variable “profitability of SMEs in cross-border trading”. The study outlined a number of trading strategies adopted by the Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border trading. Also, the study revealed a number of challenges faced by Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border trading in conducting international businesses in the multipolar world. Also, a number of trading restrictions that hinder effective business operations has been revealed. Mitigatory measures to the challenges were outlined. Further, the study revealed the role of the regional boards such as SADC and COMESA in promoting regional trade. The study revealed that, the regional boards have developed lucrative blue prints but their benefit to the intended beneficiaries is not experienced. Data for this study was collected through face-to-face interviews and online questionnaires. The data was analyzed by both SPSS and STATA. The results of the study shows that Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border trading in Zimbabwe experience a number of challenges ranging from social, political and economic. Further, the study revealed that there is a positive significance between the trading strategies and the profitability of Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border traders. A number of recommendation as well as areas for future studies were outlined at the end of the study.

Keywords: *trading strategies, financial performance, exporting businesses, Small to medium enterprises, cross-border trading.*

JEL Classification codes: *M1, M2, M3, M4, M5.*

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Introduction

Background of the Study

During the precolonial period Africa was effectively involving in barter trading. The Africans themselves were exchanging goods for goods with any challenge of race and any associated divisions. During the scramble for African states by the European countries in the early nineteenth century that when African people were attracted to foreign items such sugar, clothes, guns, items and many other foreign items. The colonisation of African states ushered a phase of massive trade between the African states and the Europeans. The creation of artificial boundaries promoted divisions amongst the African states hence many challenges emerged in international trade especially amongst the Africans themselves. The contemporary multipolar world is posing a number of impediments for the African people to thrive in boosting their economic activities through international trade. African people are the enemies of themselves and are imposing economic barriers in trading amongst themselves

The benefits of intra-African integration trading are limited as most African countries produce similar goods and services. The effort towards regional integration is important in helping to overcome market inefficiencies due to low scale and also improve competitiveness with the rest of the world. In addition to that, the country has rich natural resources thus, some Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border trading are involved in exporting minerals as well as engaged in manufacturing iron products (FinMark Trust, 2023). Also, a number of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border trading are engaged in manufacturing various products as traditional artifacts, clothing as well as engaged in retailing.

Problem of the Study

The issue of concern is the existences of a number of challenges faced by the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in the current multi-polar world. Despite the existence of independence enjoyed by African states the SMEs in cross-border trading face a number of challenges ranging from social, economic and political spheres. Despite the existence of regional groupings such as the Southern African, Development Community (SADC), Common Markets for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) and many other economic groupings. The SMEs in cross-border trading are experiencing unending business challenges especially when exporting their goods and services.

Purpose of the Study and Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to establish the relationship between trading strategies adopted by Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders on the financial performance of their business. Positive financial performance of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders result in the economic boom of the whole economy of the country. Vice-versa when there is low financial performance of the Small and medium-sized

enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders resulted in the low economic performance of the entire nation. The study aims to achieve the following objectives;

- Establish the role of SMEs on the economic development of the economy.
- Assess the challenges and mitigatory measures by SMEs in Cross-border trading.
- Analyse the strategies adopted by the SMEs in Cross-border traders in penetrating the international business.
- Examine the contribution of regional trade policy in Promoting regional Trade

Literature of the Research Study

The research study is supported by the literature from various sources such as the electronic journals, conference presentations, working papers and many other sources of literature. The main purpose of the literature review is to enable the study to explore the research gap in the same direction followed by renowned scholars and authors (Sounders, Lewis & Thornhil, 2019).

Theoretical Development

The study is guided by two major theories namely, the traditional classical theories of international trade developed by Adam Smith, (1776) and later developed by David Ricardo (1817) in Wolonski & Coats, (2009). The major focus of attention by the classical theorist was to emphasis on the concepts of comparative advantage and absolute advantage for the success of international trade. Also, the New Trade theorists emphasized the idea that, contemporary trade is not only determined by comparative and absolute advantages but trade flows are greatest between countries with similar technological capabilities or factor endowments (Brooks, 2015).

Classical International Trade Theories

Adam Smith an early classical theorist, developed his theory of absolute advantage. Adam Smith (1776) in (Mazikana, 2023), held the view that, if two nations engage into trade with each other voluntarily, both the nations must gain from each other. If one nation gained nothing or incur losses, the country that incurs losses would refuse to keep engaged in trading with the gaining nation (Deepesh, 2023). According to Adm Smith, mutually beneficial trade takes place based on absolute advantage. When one nation is more efficient than the other nation (or has an absolute advantage over the other) is producing a second commodity, then both nations gain by each specializing in the production of the commodity of its absolute advantage (Boschma, 20220). Thus, exchanging part of its output with the other nation for the commodity of its absolute advantage and exchanging part of its output with the other nation for the commodity of its absolute disadvantage (Andrea, 2018). For example, Zimbabwe is efficient in producing agricultural commodities as well as being rich in natural minerals.

New Trade Theory

The contemporary set of ideas contained in the recent literature of international trade has been termed the “new trade theory” and has been pioneered by Dixit and Norman, (1980), Lancaster, (1980), Krugman, (1981), Helpman, 1981) and Ethier, (1982) in Boschma, (2022). The New Trade Theories emerged during the last two decades due to the growth in the literature on international trade. The contemporary literature has shifted the focus away from the traditional or the conventional models based on the assumptions of perfect competition and constant returns in production to the implications of imperfect competition and economies of scale for international trade (An, Sharp & Shaw, 2021). The set of ideas contained in the recent literature of international trade has been termed “New Trade Theory”. One of the major points of contradiction between

the traditional and the New Trade Theory relates to the policy recommendations needed for industrial development. According to the New Trade Theory neutral incentives and laissez faire policies are not always conducive to industrial development as advocated by conventional trade theory (Bhara, Kumar, Sharma, Sehgal & Jakhar, 2023). Traditional theories emphasized on the comparative advantage justifications for international trade imply a strong tendency for trade between countries with large differences in technology or factor endowments. However, the advent of New Trade Theory has been shown that, this is not always the case, in many instances trade flows are greatest between countries with similar technological capabilities or factor endowments, (Smith, 1994) in Boarini & Kolev & McGregor, (2014).

The role of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders are very important to the economic performance of the country in a number of ways. They contribute immensely to the local and regional economic development. They are the major contributing to income generation and job creation. In Zimbabwe 80% of the economic activities are under the control of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Ohnsorge & Yu, 2023). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders contribute immensely in regional integration by facilitating trade and cultural exchange between neighbouring countries. The majority of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders are engaged in manufacturing and selling cultural artifacts. Therefore, they enhance the cultural exchange amongst the regional countries (Mazikana, 2023).

Challenges Faced by Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Cross-Border Traders

A number of challenges hinder the smooth business operations of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in the Multipolar world. The most notable challenges include; Regulatory and Policy Challenges, Economic and financial challenges, Infrastructure and logistics challenges, Security and safety challenges, Information and communication challenges, Social and cultural challenges, Environmental and health challenges, Technological challenges and many others (Mazikana, 2023).

Regulatory and Policy Challenges

The global Multipolar is faced by a number of regulatory and policy challenges. This is due to complex and divergent trade regulations. Also, non-tariff barriers (NTBs) and bureaucratic hurdles as well as limited harmonization of customs procedures. In addition to that, there are unclear or conflicting policies on international trade, taxation and immigration laws (Cole & Sokolyk, 2018). Regulatory and Policy Challenges can be mitigated by conducting meetings in which the ministers of trade may discuss on the best ways to develop and implement trade regulations and policy challenges. Also, the need to simplify and harmonise international trade regulations (Deepesh, 2023).

Economic and Financial Challenges

A number Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in the Multipolar world encounter a number of economic and financial challenges. The world over economic and financial challenges are the order of the day to every business operator (Mazikana, 2023). One of the major economic and financial challenges faced Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders is the fluctuating exchange rates and currency volatility (FinMark Trust, 2022). In Zimbabwe and the regional countries, the local currency is not stable thereby fluctuating on daily basis. This result in misleading budgets for traders hence they incur a number of wrong decisions. In addition to that, there is limited access to finance, credit, and insurance. Also, high transaction costs and fees caused by price fluctuations and market volatility ((Mazikana, 2023). The

challenges caused by the economic and financial challenges can be mitigated through providing access to financial service to Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders. There is need to remove access to financial challenges barriers such as demanding collateral securities to small businesses (Ohnsorge & Yu, 2023).

Infrastructure and Logistics Challenges

Another business challenge faced by Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in the Multipolar world is lack of infrastructure and logistics challenges. Many parts of Zimbabwe especially the rural areas are characterised by inadequate transportation networks and border facilities. In addition to that, there is limited space for warehousing and storage capacity. Also, high transportation costs and long lead times and inefficiencies customs clearance (Deepesh, 2023). There are a number of options available to mitigate infrastructure and logistics challenges. There is for the regional governments to develop strategies to improve and develop infrastructure and logistics. Well-developed infrastructure and logistics are very important in improving the existing infrastructure of a given country (Ohnsorge & Yu, 2023).

Security and Safety Challenges

Security and safety are other challenges that is encountered by Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders. In many cases there are a number of border conflicts, violence, and political instability. In addition to that, high levels of theft, smuggling, and organised crime, corruption, and extortion by border officials. Also, there is limited protection for traders at the border posts (Cole & Sokolyk, 2018). Security and safety challenges can be resolved by making every government to be responsible for ensuring maximum security and safety at their border post so as to ensure maximum security for traders. Also, there is need to improve security and safety measure for all regional countries (FinMark Trust, 2022).

Information and Communication Challenges

The contemporary global multipolar world is characterised by large information that is received and processed within a short period of time. Therefore, there is limited access to market information and trade data by many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders (Bharat, Kumar, Sharma, Sehgal & Jakhar, 2023). This is characterised by language and cultural barriers. A number of small businesses in Zimbabwe have limited use of technology and digital platforms hence inadequate trade facilitation and support services (Ohnsorge & Yu, 2023). These challenges of information and communication challenges can be resolved by ensuring that every Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border trading have their own digital platforms. Also, the need to adopt and harness the services of big data analytics for the survival of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders (Bodal, 2022).

Technological Challenges

The global multipolar is characterised by high level of technologies which is ever changing. Therefore, many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders are lagging behind in technological adoption and implementation. Limited adoption and digital technologies are a major challenge for many small businesses in Zimbabwe (Ohnsorge & Yu, 2023). Many small businesses have inadequate e-commerce infrastructure. Thus, they encounter high level of cybersecurity threats and data protection as they lack the knowledge how best they can protect their data and business information (World Economic Forum, 2019). Also, many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders have limited access to technology and effective training of their employees (Finscope MSME Survey, 2022). There are a number of mitigatory strategies on the technological challenges for Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders. More training is needed for the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders (Cole & Sokolyk, 2018). There is need for the

government to engage into massive training to develop the small businesses to have access to current technological innovation that are available for contemporary businesses (Bodal, 2022).

Trade Restrictions Faced by Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Cross-Border Traders

There are a number of trade challenges that Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders face in a multipolar world. These challenges include; tariffs and taxes, non-tariff barriers, quotas and licensing, customs procedures, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, technical barriers to trade, rules of origin, currency restrictions, security and surveillance and many others.

Tariffs and Taxes

A number of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders import most of their materials they use in their businesses therefore, they experience high import duties and high taxes on the raw materials they import (Betek, Fayomi & Agboola, 2018). Same applies with the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders who are engaged in entrepôt trade. High tariffs and taxes incurred by the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders resulted in many of their goods to have high production costs (Atta- Mensah, 2022). The existence of complex tax laws and revenue collection requirements. For example, traders must pay Value Added Tax (VAT), Pay As You -Earn (PAYE), and many other taxes with strict penalties for non-compliance. Therefore, their prices of their goods and services become very expensive which makes it very difficult to compete at the international sphere (Alexander & Garba, 2021).

Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs)

Non-tariff barriers are another major drawback for Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders as it results in more complex regulations, standards, as well as complex certification requirements (Alexander & Garba, 2021). Traders engaged in international businesses must submit documents to the Zimbabwe Revenue Authority (ZIMRA), including commercial invoices, bills of lading, and certificate origins (Betek, Fayomi & Agboola, 2018). Also, imports and export permits requirements and licenses, often with strict conditions and deadlines. For example, traders need permits from the ministry of industry and commerce to import raw materials. Standards and certification compliance with Zimbabwean standards and certification requirements such as those set by the Standards Association of Zimbabwe (Boschma, 2022).

Quota and Licensing

Quota and Licensing restrictions on quantities and requirements for licenses limit market access. Quotas results in limiting the amount of goods that can be imported or exported, restricting the traders' ability to meet market demand for making the export goods (Alexander & Garba, 2021). Also, licensing requirements in which traders must obtain licenses to import and export specific goods. This usually need a lot of time to get all the required procedures to get all the required papers. Product restrictions limit the trader's ability to diversify their offerings. These restrictions due to quotas and licensing promote smuggling and illegal trading amongst the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders (Aning & Abdallah, 2016).

Customs Procedures

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders face a number of challenges at the border post due to cumbersome and time-consuming customs clearance processes that delay traders in performing their businesses with convenience. Complexity and lack of transparency at the border post result in unclear or constantly changing regulations, procedures, and requirements can confuse traders and lead to errors and delays (Alexander & Garba, 2021). Also, slow customs clearance processes can delay goods delivery, increasing storage costs and reducing

competitiveness. Also, limited automation for inspecting the goods result in manual customs procedures can lead to errors, delays and increasing costs to the traders (Alexander & Garba, 2021).

Trade Embargoes and Sanctions

Trade embargo is a government ban on trade with some specific countries, organisations or sometimes individuals (Aning & Abdallah, 2016). Trade embargo is as a result of political coercion, economic sanctions, national security whereby protect its interests on sensitive issues (Aning & Abdallah, 2016). Economic sanctions refer to a situation whereby on country may stop trading with another country due to their differences. For example, unjustified sanctions imposed by Britain and its allies in Zimbabwe also, influencing other countries to stop trading with Zimbabwe since the year 2000.

Currency Restrictions

In Zimbabwe restrictions in currency have significantly disturbed the cross-border trade leading to a number of challenges such as shortage in foreign currency such as limited access to South African Rand, US dollar, Euros and other functional currencies in Zimbabwe. Many citizens failed to import the required quantities of raw materials due to restricted currencies (Betek Fayomi & Agboola, 2018). Restrictions in currency is the major catalyst for creating the black market, reduced economic growth and development (Aning & Abdallah, 2016). It also leads to reduced imports and exports, increased costs and reduced profit margins of traders.

Strategies Adopted by Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Cross-Border Traders

There are a number of strategies adopted by Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders. Generally, a strategy is a long-term plan of conducted to achieve desired goals of a business (Lawson, 2015). These strategies include; marketing, export oriented, entrepot trade, counter trade, joint venture, franchising, e-commerce and many others.

Marketing Strategies

A number of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders are now enlightened in adopting and implementing a number of marketing strategies in conducting their businesses. Marketing is a process in which businesses create value for customers and build strong customer relationship so that the customers continue demanding the product (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016). Cost-leadership strategy is one of the common business strategies adopted by many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders. Cost-leadership is conducted by establishing the competitive advantage and focuses on providing lowest cost of operation in the industry (Wolonski & Coates, 2009). The cost-leadership is often driven by company efficiency, size, scale, scope and the cumulative experience of the business (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016). Cost-leadership is considered the best business strategy to implement in the sense that, it provides the business with economies of scale, access to capital due to low internal costs and allows the maximisation of profits by the business (Andrea, 2018).

Export-Oriented Strategy

Export-oriented strategy is another important strategy adopted by the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in Zimbabwe. Export-oriented strategy is conducted by focusing on producing goods and or services for sale in foreign markets rather than to focus on the domestic markets. The aim of export-oriented strategy is to promote exports as well as to generate the much-needed foreign currency (Brooks, 2015). Also, export-oriented approach aims to capitalise on global demand, competitive advantages as well as to enjoy the economies of scale. Export-oriented strategy is conducted through effective market research, pricing strategy, product adaptation, logistics and transportation, marketing and promotion and many others (Ngoze, 2016). The adoption of export-oriented strategy, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are able to

tap into global markets, to drive growth strategy, and become more resilient in increasing the business interconnected to the business world (Wolonski & Coates, 2009).

Entrepot Trade Strategy

Many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in Zimbabwe are engaged into entrepot trade. Entrepot trade is the act of buying goods from other countries (importing) not for domestic consumption but for selling to other countries (exporting) for profit (Tarisayi, 2014). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in Zimbabwe take advantages of the country being strategically surrounded by many countries (Land-locked country). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders are conducting entrepot trade through re-export through importing goods for immediate re-export without significant modification. Transshipment through importing goods for temporary storage before re-exporting to another country. Also, by entrepot manufacturing through importing raw materials or sometimes components parts, processing or assembling them, and finally re-exporting the finished goods through value addition (Wolonski & Coats, 2009).

Joint Venture Strategy

Another important strategy adopted by the Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in Zimbabwe is through joint ventures. A joint venture is a business arrangement whereby two or more companies collaborate to achieve a specific goal in order to achieve a specific goal, sharing resources, risks, and rewards (Brooks, 2015). In Zimbabwe Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders conduct joint ventures in order to access raw markets, improve competitiveness, sharing of risks, increase production capacity, acquire new technologies by partnering with companies who are engaged in processing advanced technologies (Ngoze, 2016).

Franchising Strategy

Many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders in Zimbabwe are also engaged into franchising business strategy. Franchising is a business model whereby a firm (Franchisor) grants another firm (Franchisee) the right to operate under its brand name, by using its business systems, products, and services for the purpose of maximising the profits (Tribou, 2012). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders conduct franchising through franchisor- franchisee agreement, training and support, brand usage, royalty payments (Brooks, 2015). Examples of SMEs engaged in international franchising are; Pick n Pay (for groceries), Steers (fast food), Nandos (fast food), Debonairs Pizza (piazza) and many others.

E-Commerce strategy

The advent of technologies enabled many Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders to harness technologies to conduct their businesses. Electronic commerce (e-commerce) refers to the buying and selling of goods and services over the internet (Wolonski & Coates, 2009). In Zimbabwe Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders conduct electronic commerce through various platforms such as online market places, e-commerce websites, social media, digital payment systems, cross-border e-commerce platforms, email marketing, online directories and many others (Lawson, 2015). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in cross-border traders involved in e-commerce are; service providers offering services like digital marketing, manufacturers selling products on their own websites and online market place, agricultural products selling produce on platforms like Alibaba and Trade key and many others (Bharat, Kumar, Sharma, Sehgal, & Jakhar, 2023).

Regional Trade Policy

Zimbabwe is a member of many regional groupings that promote trade amongst its member states. The most important groupings in which Zimbabwe belongs to are; Southern African,

Development Community (SADC) and Common Markets for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA). Both SADC and COMESA are concerned in promoting trade as well as to remove the barriers of trade amongst its member states (World Economic Forum, 2019).

Southern African, Development Community (SADC) on Trade

Southern African, Development Community (SADC) is a regional economic community with sixteen (16) African countries. SADC was established in 1980, since then a number of significant progresses has been made in promoting regional integration, economic growth, and developments amongst its member states (Bharat, Kumar, Sharma, Sehgal, & Jakhar, 2023). Its international trade policy focuses on Free Trade Area (FTA). The Free Trade Area was launched in the year 2008 in order to increase economic integration among member states as well as to boost economic growth, development, and to eradicate poverty through eliminating tariffs and non-tariff barriers to trade. Important aspects of Southern African, Development Community (SADC) international trade policy include; tariff reduction, customs cooperation, trade facilitation, regional integration and many other economic decisions (Bharat, Kumar, Sharma, Sehgal, & Jakhar, 2023).

Tariff Reduction

Southern African, Development Community (SADC) member states have reduced tariffs on traded goods within its community. The reduction in tariff increased market access and increased the volumes of trade (Finscope MSME Survey, 2022).

Customs Cooperation

Southern African, Development Community (SADC) also, promoted trade amongst its member states through establishing customs cooperation. The main aim of SADC was to establish effective customs union and harmonizing customs procedures and reduced trade costs amongst its member states (Bodal, 2022).

Trade Facilitation

Southern African, Development Community (SADC) also, endeavoured to engage into trade facilitation amongst its community for the easy of trade amongst its member states. Trade facilitation was improved through the reduction of a lot of documentation demanded at the international trade amongst the SADC community (Andrea, 2018). Also, trade facilitation was improved through the creation of a single market and economy.

Methodologies

The study is guided by Pragmatism research philosophy. The philosophy is very important as it enabled the researcher to present, measure and analyse the data both numerals and explanations that provides insights from the minds of the research participants. Pragmatism philosophy was chosen as it correlates with mixed research strategy that combines both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The research approach is the abductive. Abductive research approach was chosen because it correlates with the pragmatism research philosophy (Burns & Burn, 2018). The research design of the current research study is the correlational research design. Correlational research design was chosen to find the strengths of the relationship of the independent variable (Trading Strategies) and the dependent variable (Financial Performance of SMEs cross-border trading).

Population of the Research Study

The population of the research study is Two hundred and fifteen (215) registered and active Small to medium Enterprises engaged in cross-border trading. The population of the research study was

obtained from the provincial office of the ministry of small to medium enterprises in the Midlands province. The population of the registered SMEs in cross border trading was obtained from the eight (8) districts of the midland's province. These districts include Gweru Urban, Gweru rural, Kwekwe, Zhombe, Silovela, Gokwe north, Gokwe South and Mberengwa. Ethical letter was requested from my institution Midlands State University. The ethical clearance was then taken to the ministry of small to medium enterprises provincial offices from Gweru. The police clearance letter was then obtained from central policy station in the Midlands province of Zimbabwe.

Sample size

A sample is a small representative of a large population. The study resorted to choose a sample since the population is large. The major challenges are that many small to medium enterprises in cross border-trading are scattered in many parts of the Midlands Province. Thus, Yamane, (1967) sample size formula was adopted.

The sample size of this study was determined using Yamane's Formula (1967).

$$n = N / [(1) + (N * e^2)] \quad (1)$$

Where: **n** = Sample Size

N = Target population

E = Level of significance/ marginal error 5%

Therefore, the target population of the study is 120

Substituting the target population on the Yamene's formula:

$$n = 215 / [(1) + (215 * 0.05^2)] = 93.31$$

Thus, 93 questionnaires were distributed to the research participants.

Sampling Techniques

The study adopted two sampling techniques namely; snowballing and the simple random sampling. Since the researcher is not familiar with many Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Cross-border trading. The researcher approached the few research participants who in turn provide the cell phone numbers of their business colleagues. The researcher managed to create effective networking in order to reach many research participants. Snowballing sampling technique is more effective in a situation where the researcher is does not know on where to get the research participants (Creswell & Clark, 2018). Simple random sampling was adopted in distributing the questionnaires to the identified research participants. Simple random sampling was very convenient and fast method of administering the questionnaires to the research participants with minimum bias (Gray, 2012).

Research Instrument and Data Analysis

The questionnaire was the major research instrument used to collect the data for the research. Since many cross-border traders are scattered across many parts of the Midlands Province researcher forwarded online questionnaires the emails and WhatsApp platforms. The social platform enables the research participants to completed the questionnaires at their convenience. The major challenge of online questionnaires is that they provide a low response rate (Sounders, Lewis, & Thornhil, 2019). The researcher made a number of follow ups and reminders to the online research participants so as to make the administering of the questionnaire to be successful (Burns & Burns, 2012). The questionnaire consisted with both open ended and closed questions. Quantitative questions were analysed by Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). Multiple

regression analysis was adopted to analyse quantitative data. Qualitative data was analysed through thematic analysis.

Ethical and Legal Consideration

The study is guided by a number of ethical considerations. Major ethical consideration guiding the research study include; Informed consent, confidentiality of information, free participation, respect of human dignity and many other relevant ethical and legal consideration.

Informed Consent

The researcher provided full information to the research participants on the purpose of the research and the intention of the researcher in carrying out the research study. Also, the researcher obtained consent from the respondents. The researcher did not force or coerce the respondents to participate in answering the questionnaires of the research. If the research participants refuse to participate on this research they are not to be coerced to participate (Gray, 2012).

Confidentiality and Privacy

The researcher is to maintained high-level confidentiality. The role of the researcher is to collect data in a manner that is respectful and confidential. Discussing the experiences of the respondents with third parties in manner that reveal their names and their individual situations is to be avoided by the researcher (Sounders, Lewis & Thornhil). The respondents shall be assured that high level of confidentiality shall be fully observed by the researcher.

Free Participation

The researcher administered the questionnaires to the respondents who were ready and willing to participate for this research study. Those participants who were not willing and tied up were not considered to participants for this research study. Also, research participants were informed that they can withdraw from participating for this research are free are free to withdraw from participating (Burns & Burns, 2012).

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data was analysed through the use of both Statistical for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 and Statistics Technology Analysis Tools Application (STATA) version 14. The study adopted SPSS and STATA because the two software provides a comprehensive platform for data analysis and visualisation, and modelling (Burns & Burns, 2012). Data is presented in the form of tables so as to provide numerical statistical results that can be interpreted objectively.

Questionnaire Response Rate

A total of 93 questionnaires were administered through both face-to-face interviews and online interviews. A total of 12 questionnaires were not received by the researcher. Only one questionnaire was spoiled. Out of 93 questionnaires 79 of them were successfully completed without being spoiled.

Regression Analysis

The results of linear regression analysis are shown on table in table 7

Table 1. Linear Regressions

Profitability	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Strategies	.769	.036	21.37	0	.697	.841	***
Constant	.559	.154	3.64	0	.253	.864	***
Mean dependent var	3.684		SD dependent var		1.092		

R-squared	0.856	Number of obs	79
F-test	456.890	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	88.182	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	92.921

Note: *** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

Source: STATA Output

The table provides results from a linear regression analysis examining the relationship between "Strategies" and "Profitability." The coefficient for "Strategies" is 0.769, indicating that for each unit increase in strategies, profitability increases by 0.769 units, holding other factors constant. The standard error of 0.036 suggests a high level of precision in this estimate. The t-value of 21.37 and a p-value of 0.000 indicate that the relationship between strategies and profitability is statistically significant at the 1% level, meaning we can be very confident that the relationship is not due to random chance. The constant term, 0.559, represents the predicted value of profitability when strategies are zero. The model's R-squared value of 0.856 shows that approximately 85.6% of the variability in profitability is explained by the strategies variable, indicating a strong fit of the model. The F-test (456.890) and its associated p-value (0.000) further confirm that the overall model is statistically significant.

Diagnostic Tests

Three major tests were performed by the current research study. These tests are Reliability Test, Validity Test and Shapiro Wilk Test.

Reliability Tests

The study conducted the reliability test for checking the consistent of the questionnaires if consistently.

Table 2. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.955	5

Source: SPSS Output

The table shows a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.955 for 5 items, indicating excellent internal consistency and reliability of the measurement scale. This suggests that the items used in the analysis are highly consistent in measuring the same underlying concept.

Table 3. Shapiro-Wilk Test for Normal Data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
Profitability	79	0.940	4.048	3.062	0.156
Strategies	79	0.917	5.644	3.789	0.234

Source: STATA Output

The Shapiro-Wilk W test assesses whether the data for "Profitability" and "Strategies" follow a normal distribution. For both variables, the p-values (0.156 for Profitability and 0.234 for Strategies) are greater than 0.05, indicating that we fail to reject the null hypothesis of normality. In simple terms, the data for both variables do not significantly deviate from a normal distribution.

Thematic Analysis

Themes were developed open ended questions from the questionnaires administered.

Question: Briefly explain the social challenges you encounter as cross-border traders?

General Responses given:

We face a number of challenges ranging from social challenges. Particularly we Zimbabweans we are looked down upon especially in Botswana we are given names such as “Makwerekwere” (Meaning the one who lives by begging). In South Africa some of us were killed during the xenophobia attacks. Sometimes we are the victims of police harassment. We face language barriers as most of the foreign customers do not speak the international languages such as English language and French. A number of women sometimes suffer all sought of sexual harassments and it’s very difficult for to report to the police as it is difficult to know where to report.

Question: Briefly explain the Economic challenges you encounter as cross-border traders?

General Responses given:

We experience high level of bad debts. Some of our goods are taken by unscrupulous individuals we pretend belong to the police department. The places we use as market places are very expensive to us as such our profits are depleted by high rental costs. Not all the foreigners have negative attitude for us. The majority of the foreigner are good and support our businesses that’s the reason we are keep on conducting our businesses in foreign countries.

Question: Briefly explain the Economic challenges you encounter as cross-border traders?

General Responses given:

During the times of political campaigns, we are the instruments of the campaigning political parties. Some politicians are always against us and some are supporting us. Some individuals because of their political affiliations they do not want to do business with us. In many circumstances we are segregated in many aspects of the business.

Question: Do you benefit from either SADC or COMESA Trade Policies as cross-border traders?

General Responses given:

Yes, both SADC and COMESA trade policies are well documented but as cross-border traders we do not feel that we are protected due to a number of racial segregations we experience in foreign countries.

Question: In your own opinion what can be done by the regional countries to promote cross-border traders?

General Responses given:

There is need for African countries to understand the fact that as Africans we are a family. We must not be distinguished by the artificial borders established by our colonizers. Our traditional social cohesion was destroyed by our colonizers to an extent that Pan-Africanisms only exist on the lips of the Africans. Africans are to be developed economically by fellow Africans and no one else.

Discussions

The study focused on trading strategies on the financial performance of the Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border traders. Data for the research study was analyzed by using both SPSS and STATA. The final results of the study show that there is positive significance between the trading strategies adopted by the SMEs in cross-border trading and their profitability. The study also revealed that the business activities of the Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border

traders are important in boosting the economy of the country. Evidence from both questionnaires and the thematic analyses revealed that, Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border traders face a number of challenges in conducting their business activities. In addition to that, the study revealed a number of regional bodies' trade policies to promote trade. The results of the study revealed that Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border traders are not benefiting from those policies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study recommended that, Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border traders need to continue developing effective strategies that enable them to keep in business for their survival. There is need to harness modern technologies in their operations so that they are able to copy up with high level of business competition that are existing in the multipolar world. It is important for Small to medium enterprises in the cross-border traders to be able to adopt with the contemporary business trends. There is need to make vibrant educational campaigns for all the Africans people to understand that, "Africa is one family". Therefore, the spirit of brotherhood should prevail in everything they do. The concept of Ubuntu (Humanhood) needs to be shown through promoting each other in business activities. Also, African people need to understand the fact that, the economic challenges faced by Zimbabwe is due to the imposition of unjustified sanctions by those who were against its land reform. The study also, recommended that, the regional bodies such as the SADC and COMESA need to ensure that their good policies are practically implemented to benefit the intended beneficiaries.

Future Researchers

Future researchers are therefore, recommended to study on the following studies:

- How to copy up with the international trading challenges in a multipolar world.
- Overcoming regional economic barriers for a better Africa.
- Factors impeding the removal of trade barriers amongst African states.
- Integrating African trade for the benefit of future generation.

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